

G E O F I T ^E

SMART GEOTHERMAL SYSTEMS

<https://geofit-project.eu/>

Co-funded by
the European
Union

COST-EFFECTIVE ENHANCED GEOTHERMAL SYSTEMS FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDING RETROFITTING

Buildings currently account for **40% of Europe's energy consumption** and a third of its CO² emissions. To meet ambitious sustainability targets, we need **fast and efficient solutions**.

Shallow **geothermal technology is a key enabler** with great potential in Europe, but its adoption is hindered by long installation time and cost, technical difficulty in coupling heat pumps with existing heating systems, and the risk of structural damages or disruption caused by drilling activities.

In response, **Geofit is developing a holistic and novel approach to geothermal retrofitting** which is **cost-competitive, easy to install** and capable of providing efficient low temperature heating and high temperature cooling. It uses the most **innovative methods and tools** and is being demonstrated in different climate and soil conditions across Europe.

THE GEOFIT SOLUTION

Advantages

Technologies such as **geothermal heat pumps** can significantly **reduce energy consumption**, they provide heating and cooling with very low energy input.

Geofit as a whole offers many significant advantages that **take geothermal systems to the next level**, such as large energy savings, integration into a single system for both cooling and heating, free environmental energy, high energy efficiency, long lasting system and very low maintenance.

NEW TOOLS AND METHODS

Since **retrofitting is a complex process**, Geofit includes new tools and methods such as: low invasive risk assessment technologies, site inspection techniques, innovative drilling methods, optimized design methods, novel technological components and BIM tools.

LOW INVASIVE RISK ASSESSMENT TECHNOLOGIES NEW SITE INSPECTION TECHNIQUES

Within Geofit, **the latest monitoring and risk assessment methodologies** are combined with theoretical and numerical approaches to achieve a new, more reliable and faster methodology.

Ground penetrating radar

In Geofit, a compact GPR array solution is used for real-time 3D mapping of underground utilities. It relies on a massive antenna array with two polarizations, providing a huge amount of data, thus dramatically increasing the detection performance and the level of accuracy of the survey.

Structural health monitoring

To know the **health and safety of a building**, its structure is monitored by proper sensors to gather reliable and useful data. Such data, once gathered, is broadcasted via Wi-Fi/LAN connection to the data centre where it is finally filtered and analysed. This allows achieving a **numerical model** showing the current dynamic behaviour of the building.

Ground radar © IDS GEO

Heatmaps © Aresys SRL

NEW MATERIALS FOR AN IMPROVED PERFORMANCE INNOVATIVE DRILLING METHODS

Geofit's breakthrough comes from the **introduction of new computational techniques** that are used to simulate the cutting process induced by excavation tools. It will introduce a **novel method to model the drilling and excavation process** that helps operators to choose the optimum cutting structure and operating parameters.

Geofit is **improving the drilling hardware parameters** by using novel wear test and excavation modelling techniques.

Geofit is also applying **horizontal directional drilling** for the installation of horizontal loop heat exchangers in urban environments, which is **faster** and allows to keep the **drilling design under control** and reach long lengths.

OPTIMIZED DESIGN METHODS

Novel Geothermal Heat Exchanger Systems (GHEX) Ground Source Heat Pumps (GSHP)

To allow geothermal systems to be implemented in retrofitting works, and furthermore in areas where drilling is too expensive or difficult, Geofit is optimizing alternatives such as compact geometries based on the helix, slinky heat exchangers or “earth baskets”. **These non-standard heat exchangers for limited spaces are essential to reduce costs and allow systems to be installed where deep drilling is not possible.**

GHEX © AIT

Heating & Cooling Methods

In Geofit, modularized and high-performance Low Temperature Heating/High Temperature Cooling (LTH/HTC) systems are being integrated with Ground-Source Heat Pumps (GSHP), for future large-scale implementation of geothermal retrofitting in existing buildings.

LTH/HTC technology shows promising advantages and shortcuts to improve the efficiency of heat supply and distribution. **It provides easy-to-install solutions in retrofitting projects, thermal comfort and improved COP for GSHPs.**

Adsorption Compression Chiller © Fahrenheit

Hybrid Adsorption Heat Pumps © Ochsner Wärmepumpen

Modular prefabricated system © Uponor

BIM METHODOLOGY AT BUILDING & CITY LEVEL INTEGRATED RETROFIT MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK BASED ON IDDS

Geofit is developing a **complete set of geothermal retrofitting project management tool-chains** in: retrofitting operations and integrated management framework (IDDS), ICT tools for ground research and worksite monitoring, BIM enabled methods and tools for geothermal based retrofitting.

BIM METHODOLOGY AT BUILDING AND CITY-LEVEL

© Roots & Nuts

BIM Models © IDP

Learn more about our novel methods and tools in our Technologies section!

PILOT SITES

Demonstration

GEOFIT IS BEING SUCCESSFULLY IMPLEMENTED IN 5 PILOT SITES IN ITALY, IRELAND, FRANCE AND SPAIN.

The demonstration sites are open case studies representing various climates and situations found throughout Europe, with different building types and different soil conditions.

PERUGIA (ITALY) - HISTORICAL BUILDING

GEOFIT DESIGN

- Heating load: 10 kW; Cooling load: 6 kW.
- Drilling/excavation: shallow excavation (up to 2,5m) – slinky GHEX (2-m deep) - Nr of parallel trenches: 5; Distance between trenches: 1,35 m; Average trench length: 24 m (covering a total of 120 m); Ring diameter: 1,1 m; Ring depth: 2,5 m; Nr of rings: 53.
- Building monitoring during drilling phase: survey in order to study building reaction.
- Ground source heat pump: Reversible hybrid heat pump driven by electricity and gas, adsorption and compression heat pump (new gas boiler and buffer tank, adsorption unit, chiller unit). Power output: 12 kW heating; 6 kW cooling. Refrigerant with low GWP (water and propane). HP operational control system integrated.
- New integrated system covering the total heating and cooling demand.

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

- Installation of hybrid heat pump and non-standard ground heat exchangers.
- Design process and retrofit using digitalization and simulation.
- Site assessment and structural monitoring (seismic area).
- Fiber optic in order to have data from ground heat exchangers.
- 2 different backfilling areas: One regular and another with drip.
- Monitored works: Georadar before and during excavation.
- Drone monitoring.

GEOFIT DESIGN

- 20 kW heating capacity (corridor and conference room); 15 kW cooling capacity (office, conference room and director's office).
- Drilling/excavation: shallow excavation – 2 energy baskets ground heat exchangers + 1 vertical Borehole (100 m).
- Ground source heat pump: reversible hybrid heat pump driven by electricity and gas, adsorption and compression heat pump (gas boiler and buffer tank, adsorption unit, chiller unit). Nominal power output: 15 kW heating; 15 kW cooling. Refrigerant with low GWP (water and propane).

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

- Shallow earth energy baskets + additional borehole and hybrid heat pump.
- High level of instrumentation, monitoring and control enable the pilot to conduct a robust assessment of the deployed system.
- Analysis of mix shallow excavation and borehole (educational case study).

GEOFIT SYSTEM

- Heating: 192,5 kW peak load & 144,5MWh total load. Cooling: 6 kW peak load & 3,8 MWh total load.
- Drilling/excavation: improved vertical drilling and horizontal directional drilling. 12 vertical boreholes (120 meters deep and 10 m spacing) and 1 horizontal (100 meters long).
- Building monitoring during drilling phase: previous to civil works, environmental survey and survey in order to study building reaction during drilling.
- Electrically driven HP with 40kW heating capacity and 5kW cooling capacity with 2.055 l buffer tank. Whole system designed with R1234zee refrigerant. HP operational control system integrated. COP = 4,7.
- Strategy: new ground-source heat pump covers most of heat demand; base load provided by the GSHP and peak demand by the gas boiler.

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

- Retrofitting and implementation of a geothermal system that allows municipality to reduce environmental and carbon footprint and increase the use of renewable energy technologies.
- IDDS methodology applied during the whole project life cycle.
- GEOBIM-based management monitoring cost reduction.
- nZEB case study.

ARRAN ISLANDS (IRELAND) - RESIDENTIAL

GEOFIT SYSTEM

- Drilling/excavation: improved vertical drilling Nr of bh: 1; Depth of bh: 120 m.
- Ground source heat pump: commercial electrically driven HP (6kW).
- Operation strategy: ground-source heat pump covers base load and existing coal stove only used for peak demand.
- UPONOR underfloor heating system, with radiators available as backup for peak demand.
- Retrofitting: envelope insulation and low temperature heating geothermal system (floor heating + ventilation). The low temperature heating system is featured with high modularity with extreme low height design, which provides users with space savings and easy installation.

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

- Retrofit case study demonstrating energy savings and increased quality of life (comfort conditions).
- Low temperature heating system evaluated by multiple connection scenarios with heat pump, e.g., with inverter HP running by partial loads to minimize the energy bills and maximize advantages of low temperature heating storage effect.

GALWAY (IRELAND) - SPORTS CENTER

GEOFIT SYSTEM

- Ground source heat pump: Electrically driven HP (40kW).
- Drilling/excavation: Vertical drilling; Nr of bh: 17; Depth of bh: 150 m; Spacing: 10 m.
- Dual source GS + Air Source HP. Ochsner heat pump will cover most of the pool heating energy consumption. Four operational models designed with operational strategies supported by innovative cloud-based BEMS. These operational modes are optimized against a number of objective functions such as borehole regeneration potential, global efficiency of the system and having into account forecasting parameters (weather, energy prices, etc.).

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

- Innovative Dual Source Heat Pump control and operation based on cloud-based BEMS.
- Optimization of boreholes long-term performance using dual source HP and cloud-base control.

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Join our community now
to stay up-to-date and be
part of the change!

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